

Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean

D2.4. Reinforcement of The Systematic Monitoring and Data Sharing in The MED Region

VERSION 1.1

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Executive Summary

The overall objective of the InTheMED project is to implement innovative and sustainable management tools and remediation strategies for the Mediterranean (MED) aquifers (inland and coastal) in order to mitigate anthropogenic and climate-change threats by creating new long-lasting spaces of social learning among different interdependent stakeholders, NGOs, and scientific researchers in five field case studies. These are located at the two shores of the MED basin, namely in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia, and Turkey.

InTheMED will develop an inclusive process that will establish an ensemble of innovative assessment and management tools and methodologies including a high-resolution monitoring approach, smart modelling, a socio-economic assessment, web-based decision support systems (DSS) and new configurations for governance to validate efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED considering both the quantitative and qualitative aspects.

The document reports the Deliverable D2.4, which summarizes the current monitoring strategies and networks of case studies countries (Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia and Turkey) and gives insightful recommendations for implementing science-driven management based on in-situ data. Data needed for detailed groundwater assessment and management are listed. Then, a brief description of the groundwater monitoring systems by function and their assessment levels are presented. Also, the current groundwater monitoring networks of the five case study countries are reviewed. The newly monitored or gathered high-resolution data during InTheMED project from the five case studies were presented. The gained insights from these newly collected data compared to traditional monitoring strategies were discussed. Finally, recommendations towards systematic monitoring and data sharing in the case studies and beyond for the whole MED region are listed.

1. Data Needed for Groundwater Management

Changing groundwater quality and quantity is often a long and slow process occurring below an extensive and not easily accessible water body that is often considered a hidden resource. Simple one-time surveys cannot detect changes in these areas and require more elaborate monitoring networks. Management of aquifers is fundamentally about controlling groundwater abstraction, contaminant loads and aquifer response as key inputs.

In order to evaluate the groundwater issues, it is required to collect both 'baseline' and 'time-variant' data, and the collection of time-variant data is so-called groundwater monitoring. In Table 1, some of the different types of data needed for groundwater management are reported, and each type of baseline data and time-variant data are reported. One of the most important parts of groundwater data monitoring and investigations are wells and data collected by them because they are the only way to have physical access to the aquifers. When water wells are drilled, they provide one-off unique in-situ data on the groundwater resource and its variation with depth and data acquired during drilling (borehole logging) and initial test pumping form key baseline reference information on groundwater quantity and quality, in addition to their value for the determination of abstraction well potential. A set of obstruction and observation wells are called a monitoring network.

Table 1. Types of data required for detailed groundwater assessment

Type of Data	Baseline Data (From Archives)	Time-Variant Data (From Field Stations)
Groundwater Occurrence and Aquifer Properties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water well records (hydrogeological logs, Instantaneous groundwater levels and quality), Well and aquifer pumping tests. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Groundwater level monitoring, Groundwater quality monitoring.
Groundwater Use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water well pump installations, Water-use inventories, Population registers and forecasts, Energy consumption for irrigation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water well abstraction, Monitoring (direct or indirect), Well groundwater level variations.
Supporting Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climatic data, Land-use inventories, Geological maps/sections. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> River flow gauging, Meteorological observations, Satellite land-use surveys.

1.1. Cost-Effective Groundwater Monitoring

Table 2 reports different monitoring network systems and their functions and well locations. Groundwater monitoring is often considered expensive compared to surface water monitoring. The main components of expenditure include the following:

- capital cost (of network installation),
- sampling costs (for instrumentation, personnel, and logistics) and
- analytical costs (for laboratory, data processing and storage).

Moreover, the return on initial investment is not likely to be evident immediately. So, to have an effective monitoring system:

- it is crucial to have a specific objective and
- collected data should be stored systematically for future use because historical data plays an important role in calibrating numerical aquifer models and forming a reliable simulation basis for future scenarios.

In this context, groundwater abstraction and use of data monitoring play an essential role, and to reduce financial and operational costs, it is reasonable to think about different data collection sources. For example, direct monitoring of groundwater abstraction in individual abstraction wells using metering tools, which is still financially not possible in all countries. In addition, it is not possible without the cooperation of water users. Nevertheless, it is also possible to collect data through indirect monitoring by the collection of indicative data like the estimation of the extracted water using pumping time and energy consumption of the pump, or it is possible to use remote sensing tools such as satellites and airborne sensors to collect data in a relatively large scale with a lower cost per km².

The conventional use of remote sensing in groundwater is by geology mapping of land use, crop types, soil salinization and land subsidence, which recently have been interpreted as thermal energy sensor data to estimate actual evaporation rates, which is possible if only sufficient frequency of data is available, and the land surface is not so abrupt then both daily and dry session actual evaporation at farm and aquifer level can be estimated. As a direct

measurement of changes in groundwater level, NASA's GRACE mission provides the first product to evaluate groundwater variation from space. By monitoring changes in the Earth's gravity field, dedicated algorithms can disentangle groundwater changes from the rest of hydrological cycle variations.

Table 2. Classification of groundwater monitoring systems by function

System	Basic Function	Well Locations
Primary (Reference Monitoring)	Evaluation of general groundwater behaviour: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trends resulting from land-use change and climatic variation, • Processes such as recharge, flow and diffuse contamination. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In uniform areas with respect to hydrogeology and land use.
Secondary (Protection Monitoring)	Protection against potential impacts of following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic groundwater resource, • Wellfields/springheads for public water supply, • Urban infrastructure from land subsidence, • Archaeological sites against rising water table, • Groundwater-dependent ecosystems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Around areas/facilities/features requiring protection.
Tertiary (Pollution Containment)	Early warning of groundwater impacts from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intensive agricultural land use, • Industrial sites, • Solid waste landfills, • Land reclamation areas, • Quarries and mines. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Immediately down-and up-hydraulic gradient from hazard.

These techniques are subjected to increasing error levels in low vapor fluxes. Also, their original coarser scale features reduce its accuracy at local scale and therefore cannot be used to determine actual cumulative evaporation, soil moisture deficit or aquifer recharge rates for a natural arid zone vegetation cover, but it has the potential to broaden the coverage and reduce the costs.

The effectiveness of groundwater data can be increased by careful attention to the following:

- network design,
- system implementation,
- data interpretation,

- making the best use of data collected by past monitoring activities,
- selecting monitoring stations that, as far as possible, are easily accessible,
- making the fullest use of indicator determinants to reduce analytical cost,
- promoting complementary self-monitoring amongst water users,
- incorporating quality control and quality assurance procedures.

Sample modifications constitute a significant source of error which can be controlled by appropriate sampling procedures. The groundwater level is the dominant and most monitored indicator for groundwater quantity assessment. While for groundwater quality, a large range of indicators and parameters can be considered depending on the characteristics of the monitored groundwater system and the monitoring strategy's objectives. Table 3 reports different sampling procedures for groundwater quality assessment (based on Tuinhof et al. 2005).

Table 3. Summary of sampling procedures and precautions for specific groups of groundwater taken from Tuinhof et al. 2005

Determinant Group	Sampling Procedure	Preferred Materials	Storage Time/ Temperature	Operational Difficulty /Cost
Major Ions Cl, SO ₄ , F, Na, K	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.45 µm filter only • No acidification 	Any	7 days/4 °C	Minimal
Trace Metals Fe, Mn, As, Cu, Zn, Pb, Cr, Cd, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sealed 0.45 µm filter • Acidify (pH <2) • Avoid aeration through splashing/head space 	Plastic	150 days	Moderate
N Species NO ₃ , NH ₄ (NO ₂)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sealed 0.45 µm filter 	Any	1 day/4 °C	Moderate/Low
Microbiological TC, FC, FS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sterile conditions • Unfiltered sample • On-site analysis preferred 	Dark glass	6 hours/4 °C	Moderate/Low
Carbonate Equilibria pH, HCO ₃ , Ca, Mg	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unfiltered well-sealed sample • On-site analysis (pH, HCO₃) • (Ca/Mg at base laboratory • On acidified sample) 	Any	1 hour (150 days)	Moderate

Table 3. Summary of sampling procedures and precautions for specific groups of groundwater taken from Tuinhof et al. 2005

Determinant Group	Sampling Procedure	Preferred Materials	Storage Time/ Temperature	Operational Difficulty /Cost
Oxygen status pE(EH)*, DO, T *Oxidation- Reduction Potential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On site in measuring cell • Avoid aeration • Unfiltered 	Any	0.1 hour	High/Moderate
Organics TOC, VOC, HC, CHC, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unfiltered sample • Avoid volatilization • Direct absorption in cartridges preferred 	Dark glass or teflon	1–7 days (Indefinite for cartridges)	High

1.1.1. Limitations of Qualitative Groundwater Data Monitoring

Water wells and springs are the first points to consider as a data collection source, and the range of properties to be controlled are those listed by Foster and Gomes, 1989, but a reduced list of parameters will be used to be monitored on a long-term period. The results of this kind of monitoring do not usually correspond to the actual condition of water bodies as they are collected at a specific point and time throughout the whole waterbody resource. The pumping rate and pumping period are other effective variables reducing the reliability of collected data that need to be considered in the interpretation of the results.

1.1.2. Early Warning System of Potential Threats to Groundwater

Regarding groundwater quality monitoring, in most cases, the major requirement is to obtain early warnings of possible threats to water resources. To this end, it is necessary to consider the 3D spatial dimensions of the groundwater flow, and the obtained samples have to be considered as the quality of recharge of the aquifer (not the average quality). In addition, the vertical variation in quality is the other factor that needs to be considered.

During the recent developments of urban and industrial waste disposal to groundwater and the intensification of agricultural cultivations, it is necessary to consider the possible threats scenarios in designing the piezometers networks.

2. Groundwater Monitoring Networks and Strategies in Five Case Studies' Countries

2.1. Spain

Institutional Setting and Purpose

The Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge is in charge of groundwater monitoring in Spain. The Ministry executes the Governmental policy on energy and the environment for the transition to a more ecological and social productive model. The objective of the monitoring network was adapted in accordance with the EU Water Framework Directive (WFD) when hundreds of new piezometers were introduced in every basin for determining the chemical status of water bodies.

Characteristics of The Network

Historical groundwater data for Spain are available at <https://sig.mapama.gob.es/redes-seguimiento/index.html?herramienta=Piezometros>, last accessed 12/04/2023 repository. This network includes wells with one or two filters, and artesian wells. Commonly data are measured once a month. In total, there are more than 2,700 piezometers included in the network as given in Figure 1.

Processing and Dissemination

The Monitoring Network Information System from the Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and Environment and the Ministry for Ecological Transition offers information about the hydrological monitoring in Spain, including the groundwater monitoring network (Figure 1).

Since 2011, the management of the network has been done by the General Water Authority (DGA). By selecting a well, metadata (coordinates, elevation well depth and others) and time series (all monthly historical data) are visualized in the system. This information can also be downloaded (in PDF or Excel files). Recently, the option of bulk download of the entire database is possible.

Figure 1. Groundwater monitoring network of Spain. Source: (Information System of Monitoring Networks and Hydrological Information from MITECO, Spain)

2.2. Greece

Institutional Setting and Purpose

The Special Secretariat for Water under the Greek Ministry of Environment and Energy is in charge of the National Monitoring Programme of Greece is in charge of hydrological monitoring network. Regarding groundwater, the Institute of Geology and Mineral Exploration (IGME) has been the main promoter of the programme since 2000. The National Monitoring Network has been active since 2012. In addition, each of the 14 prefectures of Greece have their own monitoring programmes through private boreholes.

Characteristics of The Network

The National Monitoring Network operates 1,392 stations dedicated to groundwater quality and quantity in the main groundwater bodies of the country. Stations are divided in two categories: surveillance and operational stations. While surveillance stations monitor water bodies of good status only during a certain period, operational status stations continuously monitor water bodies that failed at achieving good status.

Processing and Dissemination

Data can be found in several sources, such as in the National Data Bank of Hydrological and Meteorological Information (NDBHMI) and in the website and map portal of the National

Water Monitoring Network. One product available in this portal is the boundaries and characterization of groundwater bodies (GWB) per River Basin District, developed in the framework of River Basin Management Plans under the EU WFD, depicting the quantitative and qualitative status of groundwater bodies. Monitoring data can be obtained directly via the website but can also be requested via the Special Secretariat for Water. In addition, data from the 14 prefectures of Greece can be obtained through their water resources directorates. The geoportal of the National Mineral Exploration Research Centre also provides open geospatial data and services for Greece, and data can be obtained from here via request. It is noteworthy that, in general, all official data can be found in the National Geodata Portal as well as given in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Groundwater monitoring stations of Greece source taken from (National Geodata Portal, Greece)

2.3. Portugal

Institutional Setting and Purpose

The Portuguese Environmental Agency (APA) is in charge of the National Groundwater Monitoring Network of Portugal. The monitoring policy of APA includes not only the measurement networks but also measuring instruments, collection and validation procedures, the database system for data storage, and simulation models to support water management and planning.

Characteristics of The Network

The National Water Resources Information System (SNIRH) contains 22,639 groundwater registered points, 7,864 of them have detailed information. At a national level, 592 points belong to the 'quantity network' and 780 to the 'quality network' given in the following repository <https://snirh.apambiente.pt>, last accessed on 12/04/2023 (Figure 3).

Processing and Dissemination

The monitoring stations can be visualized in an interactive portal maintained by the SNIRH, as illustrated in Figure 3. The groundwater quantity report is based on the quantitative groundwater monitoring network and contains an assessment of groundwater level change country-wide. In most aquifer systems, the measurements started in the 1970s, and the frequency of observations is monthly. In the last several years, some piezometers have been equipped with automatic sensors and the data are monitored daily. The groundwater quantity report plays an important role in alerting the decreasing groundwater level, especially during drought periods.

Figure 3. Groundwater Monitoring Network of Portugal. Source (SNIRH)

2.4. Tunisia

Institutional Setting and Purpose

The Tunisian groundwater monitoring network and management are coordinated by the General Directorate of Water Resources (DGRE), with the support of the National Water Distribution Utility (SONEDE). Even though the groundwater monitoring network is relatively dense and active since 1970 (Figure 4), it is not centralised and accessible, limiting its assessment and further recommendation for improvement (increase monitoring frequency and using high frequency and automatized sensors etc).

Characteristics of The Network

Monitoring of groundwater levels is done twice a year by 24 departments of the DGRE. Through a network of more than 2,000 shallow wells and more than 1,100 deep wells the network of Tunisian groundwater monitoring is given in Figure 4.

Processing and Dissemination

DGRE publishes an annual report with the results of the monitoring of the deep aquifers, and every 5 years a report with the results of the monitoring of the shallow aquifers.

Figure 4. Tunisian monitoring network of groundwater levels according to Besbes et al. (2009)

2.5. Turkey

Institutional Setting and Purpose

State Hydraulic Works (Devlet Su İşleri, DSI), founded in 1954, is the state entity responsible for groundwater monitoring throughout Turkey and the sole authorized enforcing entity in groundwater governance. DSI's responsibilities include drilling wells for groundwater monitoring, research and distribution, protection of groundwater, registry of groundwater use, gathering and evaluation of data, and dissemination of irrigated farming and land consolidation. DSI currently operates under the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry. It is organized under 18 regional departments with the general directorate located in the capital Ankara.

The purpose of the groundwater well and surface water monitoring network operated by DSI is to monitor both water quality and quantity and to use that information in water resource management.

Characteristics of The Network

Historical groundwater data in Turkey are available upon request from DSI general directorate. The total number of monitoring wells in Turkey in 2021 was 1,396 monthly monitoring wells and 2,198 seasonal monitoring wells. Besides the groundwater levels, the monitoring data includes the coordinates of the monitoring points, ground surface elevation, the well depth and in some instances soil classification. The country is divided into 25 watersheds as shown in Figure 5, with Konya Closed Basin being basin 16. The number of wells within each basin is given in Table 4.

Figure 5. Twenty-five water basins of Turkey

Table 4. Number of monitoring wells in each basin of Turkey

Basin No	Basin Name	Monitoring Wells (2021)	
		Monthly Monitoring Wells	Seasonal Monitoring Wells
01	Meriç Ergene	39	25
02	Marmara	52	15
03	Susurluk	55	109
04	Kuzey Ege	44	28
05	Gediz	67	85
06	Küçük Menderes	56	92

Table 4. Number of monitoring wells in each basin of Turkey

Basin No	Basin Name	Monitoring Wells (2021)	
		Monthly Monitoring Wells	Seasonal Monitoring Wells
07	Büyük Menderes	84	37
08	Batı Akdeniz	38	74
09	Antalya	73	73
10	Burdur Göller	13	18
11	Akarçay	44	9
12	Sakarya	212	252
13	Batı Karadeniz	0	31
14	Yeşilirmak	53	201
15	Kızılırmak	184	633
16	Konya Kapalı	255	170
17	Doğu Akdeniz	10	34
18	Seyhan	38	67
19	Asi	23	31
20	Ceyhan	57	12
21	Fırat - Dicle	177	175
22	Doğu Karadeniz	2	0
23	Çoruh	2	4
24	Aras	34	54
25	Van Gölü	0	0
Total		1396	2198

Processing and Dissemination

All water-related data collected from Turkey's groundwater and surface water resources are collected in a central water database (Su very tabanı, SVT) operated by DSI. The purpose of the SVT system is to store, report and utilize the data obtained as a result of the measurement, evaluation and modelling studies of all kinds of water resources used. The SVT system is accessible to DSI authorized employees only. The option of direct public downloading of the database is currently not available. Upon written request and approval by the DSI general directorate, the data are downloaded and shared.

Recently 122 high resolution wells (automatic monitoring with frequency on the order of minutes) have been installed in the Konya Closed Basin. These wells, which were installed in 2019, monitor groundwater level, electrical conductivity and temperature. Transition to high resolution monitoring is underway or being planned for other basins of Turkey.

Table 5. Summary of data availability for each case study country at the national level

Country	Institutional Setting	Number of Piezometers	Frequency of Monitoring	Indicators Used	Database
Spain	The Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge	2,700	Once a month	Coordinates, elevation well depth	General Water Authority (DGA)
Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Institute of Geology and Mineral Exploration (IGME) Each of the 14 prefectures of Greece have their own monitoring programmes 	1,392	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water bodies of good status only during a certain period Continuously monitor water bodies that failed at achieving good status. 	Boundaries and characterization of groundwater bodies (GWB) per River Basin District	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National Data Bank of Hydrological and Meteorological Information (NDBHMI) National Water Monitoring Network National Mineral Exploration Research Centre National Geodata Portal
Portugal	The Portuguese Environmental Agency (APA)	592 points for quality monitoring, 780 points for quantity network	Since 1970 it is monitored monthly, Recent year some piezometers are monitored daily	-	National Water Resources Information System (SNIRH))
Tunisia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General Directorate of Water Resources (DGRE) National Water Distribution Utility (SONEDE) 	2,000 shallow wells and 1,100 deep wells	twice a year	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DGRE publishes an annual report for deep aquifers Every 5 years for shallow aquifers.
Turkey	State Hydraulic Works (DSI), under the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry	3,594 (2021)	1,396 monthly monitoring wells and 2,198 seasonally monitoring wells, newly installed high-resolution wells monitor every few minutes	Coordinates, elevation, well depth	State Hydraulic Works upon written request and approval

3. Benefits of High-Resolution Monitoring Compared to Grab Sampling

During the project, all case studies, except the Requena-Utiel aquifer in Spain, have benefited directly or indirectly from implementing the high-resolution monitoring approaches using appropriate sensors (Greece and Tunisia), gathering existing high-resolution groundwater data (Turkey) or deploying geophysics techniques (Greece and Portugal) to enhance the monitoring and understating of groundwater properties, dynamics and processes. The case studies are considered an array of complementary demonstrators, reflecting the power of high-resolution groundwater data to boost knowledge and establish proper groundwater management. The gained insights from each case study are reported below and can be considered good practices for groundwater monitoring in the MED region. The high-resolution sensors were not implemented in the Requena-Utiel case study due to the large-scale upgrade of the entire monitoring network with high-frequency sensors by the local Water Authority. So, replicating monitoring efforts has been omitted by the project.

3.1. Tympaki, Greece

Greece's Crete is home to the Tympaki Basin, an area renowned for its agriculture and groundwater supplies. On groundwater systems, climate change can have a profound impact in a number of ways. In Tympaki Basin, groundwater, and climate change are some of the major issues that need to be addressed.

The amount, intensity, and distribution of rainfall can change as a result of changes in precipitation patterns brought on by climate change. These modifications may have an impact on the method through which water recharges aquifers through groundwater infiltration. In the Tympaki Basin, groundwater recharge rates may be lowered if rainfall decreases or evaporation increases due to warmer temperatures.

The Tympaki Basin's groundwater quality is susceptible to climate change. Increased soil temperatures and altered precipitation patterns can impact the amount of pollutants and nutrients present, which can then seep into groundwater. Increased frequency and severity of extreme weather conditions, including floods or droughts, can also cause the mobilization of pollutants and have an effect on the quality of groundwater.

In the Tympaki Basin, variations in groundwater recharge rates and the potential for saltwater intrusion may have an impact on the amount of water available for household, industrial, and agricultural usage. Groundwater is a crucial resource for irrigation in the area, and any reduction in supply or decline in quality might have a big impact on nearby populations and the agricultural industry.

Effective management solutions are needed to adapt to the effects of climate change on groundwater. This involves using water-efficient irrigation methods, using sustainable groundwater extraction techniques, and advocating water conservation initiatives. Additionally, the Tympaki Basin's groundwater resources can be monitored and modelled to produce useful data for resource planning and decision-making.

3.1.1. Needs of Implementing High-Resolution Monitoring

Implementing high-resolution data in the Tympaki hydrological basin can provide several valuable benefits for water resource management, environmental analysis, and scientific research. The main reasons for using high-resolution data include:

Improved Precision: High-resolution data offers a more detailed representation of the basin's characteristics, such as topography, land use, soil properties, and hydrological features. This precision is crucial for accurately modelling and understanding the basin's behaviour, including water flow, infiltration, and runoff patterns.

Enhanced Hydrological Modelling: Hydrological models require accurate input data to produce reliable and insightful results. High-resolution data helps improve the accuracy of these models, which are essential for various applications, such as flood forecasting, water availability assessments, and climate change impact studies.

Detailed Analysis of Processes: With high-resolution data, researchers and water resource managers can conduct more detailed analyses of hydrological processes. This includes studying localized effects, such as small-scale runoff behaviour, local variations in water quality, and the impact of human activities on specific areas within the basin.

Identification of Vulnerable Areas: High-resolution data enables the identification of vulnerable areas within the hydrological basin, such as flood-prone zones, erosion-prone regions, or areas

susceptible to water scarcity. This information is crucial for effective land-use planning, disaster preparedness, and resource management strategies.

Assessment of Climate Change Impacts: Climate change can have varied and localized effects on hydrological basins. High-resolution data allows researchers to assess how climate change might impact specific areas within the basin, helping to develop targeted adaptation and mitigation measures.

Water Resource Management: High-resolution data is essential for effective water management and allocation. It enables decision-makers to understand the distribution and availability of water resources across the basin, facilitating informed decisions about water usage, infrastructure development, and conservation efforts.

In summary, implementing high-resolution data in a hydrological basin is crucial for obtaining accurate, detailed, and localized information about various hydrological processes. It empowers water resource managers, researchers, and policymakers to make informed decisions and develop sustainable strategies for water management, environmental protection, and climate change adaptation.

3.1.2. High-Resolution Monitoring Technique and Data Used

In the Tympaki basin, three meteorological stations provide daily information on rainfall and temperature variations. On the other hand, two high-resolution sensors have been installed. The first one monitors groundwater quantity and quantity in 15 minutes timestep and is located in the centre of the basin (Figure 6). The second one monitors electrical conductivity in 15 minutes timestep (Figure 7) to monitor saltwater intrusion and is located in the coastal part of the basin. Furthermore, in the study basin, at least three geophysical surveys have been applied since 2005 to identify in high-resolution spatial scale the hydrogeological background of the area and the groundwater status. The specific high-resolution data were used to calibrate and validate both the numerical and the surrogate groundwater model that were developed for the study area. Especially the geophysical data (Figure 8) were used in a stochastic geostatistical analysis approach to identify the saltwater intrusion front in the coastal part of the Tympaki basin.

Figure 6. High resolution monitoring of groundwater level (meters above sea level) in the Tympaki basin

Figure 7. High resolution monitoring of Electrical Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) in the Tympaki basin

Figure 8. High resolution geophysical monitoring of in the Tympaki basin

3.1.3. Lessons learned and innovative monitoring good practices

Lessons Learned in Hydrological Basin Monitoring are:

Importance of Data Quality: One of the most critical lessons learned is the significance of data quality. High-resolution data may provide detailed information, but it must be accurate and reliable to ensure meaningful analysis and decision-making. Implementing robust quality control measures and regularly calibrating monitoring instruments are essential to maintain data integrity.

Integration of Remote Sensing Technologies: Integrating remote sensing technologies, such as satellite imagery and aerial surveys, can complement on-ground monitoring efforts. These technologies provide a broader spatial perspective and enable monitoring of hard-to-reach or inaccessible areas, enhancing the overall understanding of the basin.

Real-time Monitoring and Communication: The value of real-time monitoring cannot be understated. Implementing sensors that provide continuous data updates allows for timely response to changes in hydrological conditions, such as flood events or water scarcity. Additionally, effective communication channels for disseminating real-time data to relevant stakeholders improve emergency preparedness and response.

Stakeholder Engagement: Engaging with local communities, water users, and other stakeholders is crucial for successful monitoring initiatives. Involving them in the monitoring

process fosters a sense of ownership and responsibility, leading to better compliance with regulations and more effective water management practices.

Long-Term Monitoring: Hydrological basin monitoring is an ongoing process, and long-term data collection is invaluable for detecting trends and understanding changes in hydrological behaviour over time. Investing in sustained monitoring efforts is vital to capture seasonal variations, climatic shifts, and other long-term changes.

Innovative Monitoring Good Practices: Sensor Networks: These devices exist in the area from different stakeholders and can be strategically placed throughout the basin to collect various data, including groundwater level, flow rates, water quality parameters, and weather conditions. IoT-enabled sensors can transmit real-time data, enabling efficient data collection and analysis. In this project, we managed to get access only to sensors operated by the water resources directorate of Crete. However, more exist operated by the National mineral resources agency, National Observatory of Athens and the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research. All these sensors should be operated under IoT framework to share data to scientific community and stakeholders. In addition, the available data can feed the surrogate groundwater web DSS model developed for the area (D3.3, <https://tinyurl.com/5awm6fm2>) to provide projections on groundwater level variations under climate change scenarios and management practices.

Big Data and Machine Learning: Harnessing big data and machine learning techniques can quickly process vast amounts of monitoring data and extract valuable insights. These technologies can identify patterns, correlations, and anomalies in the data, assisting in predicting potential hydrological events and guiding decision-making. In this project a Bayesian Average technique was applied to exploit the high-resolution spatial information from the geophysical survey.

Citizen Science: Involving the public in data collection through citizen science initiatives can expand the monitoring network and enhance data coverage. Mobile applications and online platforms can empower citizens to report observations and contribute to a broader understanding of the basin's hydrology.

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs): UAVs or drones offer a cost-effective and flexible way to capture high-resolution aerial imagery and data. They can be used for mapping land cover, monitoring vegetation changes, and assessing the impact of natural disasters on the basin.

Open Data and Data Sharing: Promoting open data policies and data sharing among relevant agencies and institutions encourages collaboration and transparency. It facilitates cross-disciplinary research and the development of more comprehensive and holistic water management strategies.

In conclusion, the lessons learned in hydrological basin monitoring emphasize the importance of data quality, stakeholder engagement, and long-term commitment. Innovative monitoring practices, such as IoT, machine learning, and citizen science, offer opportunities to enhance monitoring effectiveness and gain deeper insights into hydrological processes. By combining traditional methods with innovative technologies, water resource managers can make more informed decisions to ensure sustainable water management in the basin. The aforementioned concept can be summarized in the following Figure 9:

Figure 9. A proposed combined framework for innovative data monitoring and sharing in the Tympaki basin

3.2. Castro Verde, Portugal

The Portuguese case study is located within a mining concession named Neves-Corvo and operated by SOMINCOR – Sociedade Mineira de Neves-Corvo, S.A., a subsidiary of Lundin Mining. The Neves-Corvo polymetallic base metal deposit is part of the world-class Iberian Pyrite Belt of southern Portugal and Spain. The mine is situated in the southern region of Portugal, in the Alentejo province, about 15 km southeast of Castro Verde town. Neves-Corvo

mine has been developed as an underground operation, with exploitation in five major polymetallic sulfide orebodies. Within the mine premises, the groundwater is a significant aquifer that connects to water supplies and a significant river that passes close to the mining site.

3.2.1. Needs of Implementing High-Resolution Monitoring

The groundwater system is threatened by contaminants originating from mining activities and infiltrating the groundwater bodies, mainly due to the presence of a sizeable tailing infrastructure. The main orebody has a pyrite (i.e., iron sulfide) content, so waste rock and tailings have the potential to oxidize and produce acid. Moreover, the explosives used for blasting the orebody induce the elevation in concentrations of nitrogen compounds and sulphates. Besides, mining operations are below the water table, impacting the current groundwater level of the system and wells in neighbouring regions. The pumping of water from the mine has depressed the water table over a significant area around the mine. As the mine workings deepen, some water supply wells dried up and alternative supplies of water have been provided as appropriate to compensate for this.

3.2.2. High-Resolution Monitoring Technique and Data Used

We proposed the deployment of high-resolution monitoring sensors, but due to the difficulties related to communication with the mining site and access to the premises, that objective was not achieved. Alternatively, we used a set of two-dimensional electrical resistivity profiles (ERT) acquired in several distinct periods. These two-dimensional profiles were inverted using an innovative geostatistical ERT inversion method. The predicted electrical conductivity models allowed a better definition of the groundwater system (solid and liquid phases). These results will potentially be integrated in the dynamic numerical modelling of the aquifer.

3.2.3. Lessons Learned and Innovative Monitoring Good Practices

Geophysical data help define the spatial extent and structural setting of the aquifer system. Geostatistical ERT inversion allows predicting the spatial distribution of fluid-relevant subsurface properties in high-resolution. Compared with previous models obtained with deterministic ERT inversion methods, the results obtained from the geostatistical ERT inversion are of superior resolution and allow us to acquire critical insights about the nature of the

aquifer. ERT data should be complemented with direct observations (i.e., borehole data) to allow calibration of the predicted models.

3.3. Grombalia, Tunisia

Grombalia, situated on the Cap Bon Peninsula in Tunisia, is a coastal region bordered by the Gulf of Tunis to the north. However, this idyllic coastal setting belies the pressing water crisis caused by excessive extraction and pollution. The once dependable shallow aquifer in the region now faces severe over-exploitation, with extraction rates skyrocketing over the years. This excessive extraction, coupled with the heavy reliance of industries on deep groundwater sources, has put tremendous strain on the aquifer. The situation has reached a critical point and the region grapples with a worrisome decline in both the quantity and quality of water, calling for immediate action to address the unsustainable water usage in the area to preserve this precious resource for future generations.

3.3.1. Needs of Implementing High-Resolution Monitoring

The coastal aquifer of Grombalia faces a severe situation of over-exploitation and strain due to excessive water extraction and pollution. The need for effective monitoring and management of this vital resource is paramount. Enter High-Resolution Monitoring Sensors, a cutting-edge solution that promises to revolutionize aquifer management in Grombalia.

The implementation of high-resolution monitoring is crucial in addressing the pressing challenges faced by the coastal aquifer. By deploying these advanced sensors, the existing aquifer monitoring network can be significantly enhanced, providing a higher level of detail and precision in data collection. This real-time and high-resolution data capture allows scientists and stakeholders to gain valuable insights into the aquifer's dynamics and sustainability.

Furthermore, high-resolution monitoring brings tangible benefits by enabling online, real-time monitoring in selected shallow wells. This innovative approach not only showcases the transformative potential of high-resolution monitoring but also serves as a practical demonstration of its effectiveness in safeguarding the aquifer. The seamless, continuous and immediate access to data empowers decision-makers to identify critical intervention points

promptly, ensuring timely measures can be taken to protect the aquifer from further deterioration.

Given the severity of the aquifer situation in Grombalia, the implementation of high-resolution monitoring becomes an urgent priority. These advanced monitoring sensors serve as an invaluable tool for understanding the complexities of the aquifer system and formulating targeted strategies for sustainable management. By preserving the health and integrity of the coastal aquifer, Grombalia can secure its water resources for future generations.

3.3.2. High-Resolution Monitoring Technique and Data Used

In collaboration with the Regional Commissary for Agricultural Development (CRDA) of Nabeul, three AquaTROLL-500 High-Resolution Monitoring Sensors (AquaTROLL-500) from 'In-situ' company were strategically installed at three hotspot points. These locations were selected based on prior research, focusing on areas associated with industrial activities such as agrifood, textile, and leather, which were suspected to be highly contaminated. The AquaTROLL-500 sensor offers real-time measurements of temperature, nitrate levels, and water depth. These sensors are synchronized with an online remote platform specifically developed by the sensor supplier and exclusively accessible to the CERTE team.

With the capability to provide high-fidelity and high-frequency data, the implemented high-resolution monitoring delivers downloadable daily data of approximately 10.2 KB/day via an FTP (File Transfer Protocol) server. This advanced monitoring system allows detecting fleeting events that may go unnoticed by the low-frequency sampling of conventional monitoring systems. Prior to installation, all sensors underwent rigorous calibration to ensure precise and accurate readings, highlighting the critical importance of this meticulous step. The installation of these AquaTROLL-500 sensors in collaboration with the Regional Commissary for Agricultural Development of Nabeul represents a significant scientific endeavour, enabling comprehensive and detailed monitoring of the studied areas.

Figure 10. Distribution of installed sensors in the study area of Grombalia, Tunisia

3.3.3. Lessons Learned and Innovative Monitoring Good Practices

Enhanced Data Accuracy and Real-Time Monitoring: High-resolution monitoring, with its advanced sensors, offers improved accuracy and real-time data acquisition. This provides a more precise understanding of the aquifer's characteristics and dynamics, enabling effective decision-making for resource management and protection.

Improved Contamination Identification: The strategic placement of sensors in hotspot areas allows for the early detection and identification of contamination sources. This empowers stakeholders to promptly respond and implement targeted interventions to mitigate further contamination, safeguarding the aquifer's quality.

Complementary Approach to Conventional Monitoring: High-resolution monitoring complements conventional monitoring methods by providing higher data precision and resolution. It captures transient events and variations that might go unnoticed in lower-

frequency monitoring systems, offering a more comprehensive understanding of aquifer behaviour and enabling better-informed management decisions.

Informed Decision-Making: The integration of high-resolution monitoring data into decision-making processes enhances the ability to accurately assess the aquifer's condition. It enables stakeholders to make informed choices regarding water allocation, resource protection, and sustainable management practices, ensuring the long-term viability of the aquifer system.

Innovative Tool for Data Digitalization: High-resolution monitoring aligns with Tunisia's national data digitalization context. By employing advanced sensors and data management systems, it contributes to the ongoing efforts to modernize and streamline data collection, analysis, and dissemination. This promotes efficient data-driven approaches to aquifer management and supports the broader national agenda of digital transformation in water resource management.

Overall, high-resolution monitoring in the Grombalia aquifer enhances data accuracy, aids in contamination identification, complements conventional monitoring, supports informed decision-making, and aligns with the national push for data digitalization. These key messages underscore the significance of adopting this innovative approach to better understand, manage, and protect the precious water resources in Grombalia and beyond as detailed in Figure 11.

Figure 11. The high-resolution monitoring in Grombalia aquifer

3.4. Konya, Turkey

The Konya Closed Basin, located in the central part of Turkey, is a unique hydrological region known for its closed drainage system, meaning it has no natural outflow to the sea. Agriculture is the primary driver of groundwater extraction in the region, with extensive irrigation practices supporting the cultivation of various crops, including corn, wheat, sugar beets, and vegetables. The basin has been one of the primary agricultural regions of Turkey for decades. Due to limited surface water availability, groundwater serves as a lifeline for agricultural activities and sustains the farmers' livelihoods in the area. However, this heavy reliance on groundwater has led to concerns about unsustainable pumping rates and depletion of aquifer reserves. With increasing population growth and expanding agricultural needs, there is a growing need for proper monitoring and management of groundwater resources to ensure their long-term sustainability and prevent adverse environmental impacts. Effective water management strategies, supported by accurate groundwater monitoring data, are essential to strike a balance between agricultural demands and the preservation of this vital water resource in the Konya Closed Basin.

3.4.1. Needs of Implementing High-Resolution Monitoring

Implementing a high-resolution monitoring station for groundwater level monitoring in the Konya Closed Basin is crucial to address several pressing needs. Firstly, the Konya Closed basin is an arid region characterized by limited water resources, and groundwater plays a vital role in sustaining agricultural and domestic needs. As such, accurate and frequent monitoring of groundwater levels is essential to assess the basin's overall water balance and ensure sustainable water management practices. High-resolution monitoring can also help evaluate water quality, with parts of the basin suffering from high salinity and nutrient concentrations.

A high-resolution monitoring station would enable real-time data collection, providing valuable insights into groundwater fluctuations, helping authorities to identify potential risks of overexploitation and take timely mitigation measures. Additionally, with the increasing impacts of climate change and fluctuating weather patterns, having comprehensive groundwater level data and water quality monitoring can assist in developing adaptive strategies to cope with potential droughts.

3.4.2. High-Resolution Monitoring Technique and Data Used

In the Konya Closed Basin, a total of 122 high-resolution monitoring wells were installed recently by the State Hydraulic Works (Devlet Su İşleri, DSI). These monitoring wells are the first step in upgrading the national groundwater monitoring network with similar networks planned for other regions of Turkey. The installed sensors are DCX-22 series manufactured by Keller Inc., which allow for measuring temperature, groundwater level and electrical conductivity. The sensors were set to provide measurements of these three parameters at about 10-minute time intervals. Sample plots of the temperature, groundwater level and electrical conductivity at three monitoring locations are given below. The monitoring stations are located in the east (Aksaray), south (Çumra) and central (Karapınar) regions of the basin, respectively.

Examination of the data shows that the groundwater level at these three locations exhibits similar general patterns. During the spring/summer intensive irrigation months, groundwater levels drop by as much as 10 meters, followed by partial recovery during the relatively-wet winter months. The overall effect is a drop in the groundwater levels with the actual rate of drop depending primarily on the type of crops, the irrigation system used, and precipitation rates.

It is also observed that during the high groundwater extraction periods, the data show an increase in the electrical conductivity and temperature. While temperature variations are small, the electrical conductivity (salinity) increases tend to be large with possible impacts on crop yields.

Figure 12. High resolution temperature, groundwater level and electrical monitoring data from a station in the Aksaray region

Figure 13. High resolution temperature, groundwater level and electrical monitoring data from a station in the Çumra region

Figure 14. High resolution temperature, groundwater level and electrical monitoring data from a station in the Karapinar region

3.4.3. Lessons Learned and Innovative Monitoring Good Practices

The high-resolution monitoring data installed in the Konya basin provide a number of unique benefits:

Enhanced Real-Time Monitoring: The high-resolution data provide real-time monitoring of the groundwater levels and electrical conductivity that can be used to alert water authorities and farmers to any rapid changes in water quality and quantity. This can help in performing timely mitigation measures to avoid drastic negative impacts on crop yields.

Complementarity of the high-resolution data with long-term monitoring data: Past groundwater monitoring consisted mostly of monthly groundwater level data. The high-resolution and long-term monthly monitoring data can be considered to be complementary: the long-term data provide long-term trends in groundwater conditions while the high-resolution data give short-term changes in water conditions. Both sets of data are essential for the long-term sustainable management of groundwater resources of the region.

Identification of hotspots: The installation of a cluster of sensors over a large area such as the Konya closed basin, can provide water authorities with an overview of water quality and quantity measures which can help in the identification of local hotspots and devise strategies to limit their spatial extents.

Improved definition of aquifer flow parameters: Hydrogeological studies designed specifically for defining aquifer flow parameters (such as pumping tests for the estimation of the hydraulic conductivity, transmissivity and storativity) are limited in the Konya Closed basin. Pumping wells located near high-resolution monitoring wells can be operated as short-term pumping tests. The monitoring of groundwater level drops due to short-term pumping (up to 24 hours) followed by monitoring of water recovery after cessation of pumping can provide valuable information about aquifer parameters. Ideally, these tests can be conducted in the winter when extraction in adjacent wells is limited, thereby reducing well interferences. This can be repeated at various high-resolution wells, resulting in valuable mapping of the aquifer flow parameters.

Groundwater Flow Modelling: As part of the tasks of the InTheMED, a groundwater flow model was developed for the entire basin. The model used long-term data at 28 wells for calibration. With the collection of the high-resolution data, the developed model can be tested with newly acquired data leading to further refining of the model.

Improved vadose zone hydrological and geochemical modelling: Accurately estimating the net recharge into the aquifer is a critical parameter for the sustainable use of aquifer systems. With a few years of high-resolution data, improved recharge estimates can be potentially obtained. Moreover, the salinity of the groundwater can also yield important information on the geochemical properties of the vadose zone soils.

Managing Big Databases: With the availability of a large number of monitoring wells continuously providing data every few minutes, it is obvious that the databases will soon become very large. To maximize the benefit of these valuable yet big databases, it is important to have qualified personnel dedicated to managing and analysis of these databases. Knowledge of various geostatistics as well as machine learning techniques would be particularly helpful for this task.

Overall, the collection of high-resolution data at the Konya closed basin has provided important information on the quality and quantity of the groundwater in the basin. The data can be used in further hydrogeologic studies to gain further benefits from this valuable database and help in the sustainable management of this vital water resource.

4. Recommendation Towards Systematic Monitoring and Data Sharing in the MED Region

In-situ data remain an essential component for sustainable groundwater management and protection. For instance, in-situ data are required for models' calibration and validation, reporting obligations for different directives and developing new monitoring alternatives such as Earth Observation (EO). Groundwater monitoring networks and strategies in the five case study countries were generally developed in the 1970s and 1980s when water consumption and environmental problems were completely different from today's concerns. Today emerging environmental problems arising from the increasing effects of climate change have resulted in additional needs for advanced understanding of physical processes using additional parameters at finer spatiotemporal resolution. Thus, continuous monitoring network updates are urgently needed to keep detailed assessment of water resources and environmental status benefiting from advanced technologies and data assimilation capabilities.

In-situ data analysis of case study countries was beneficial to understand the spatiotemporal changes in groundwater over the last decades, allowing trend analysis (See D2.3 for more details). These countries contain comprehensive in-situ groundwater level data that have been centralised and harmonized either at regional or national scale. Also, they have relatively dense and long-term in-situ data allowing for decadal assessment of groundwater trends. Even though the lack of measurement continuity among the monitoring wells, results helped gain insights into groundwater depletion and its spatiotemporal evolution in time. Detailed groundwater assessment requires information on threshold values of key groundwater indicators such as minimum groundwater level for sustainable exploitation and ecological limit. These boundary conditions are relevant to evaluate the degree of occurrence of deterioration phenomena (such as eutrophication and depletion and salinization). Of course, the conclusions of in-situ data analyses are limited as they depend on the data availability and aquifer system characteristics in terms of geology, land use, hydrology etc. This information has the same weight to groundwater level data to ensure enhanced assessment that lead to preventive management. Thus, this information should be shared always with the raw data.

Systematic monitoring in typical and strategic sampling locations could better assess the decadal changes of groundwater status and compared to random monitoring with undefined

gauging stations and under varying monitoring frequency and duration. Also, to maximise the beneficial use of in-situ data results, they should be interpreted simultaneously, with remote sensing data and modelling data. This will open new horizons of information gathering and knowledge coproduction.

In-situ data also should be shared at the right time. The right time means at the appropriate time when management is required or new scientific evidence is needed to fill a knowledge gap. Sharing in-situ data too late can lead to mismanagement and wrong decision-making, resulting in severe and irreversible environmental problems.

4.1. Limitations to Data-Sharing

Overall, considering all case studies countries, there is a reliance on in-situ measurements. This is exacerbated by concerns around data sharing by data owners. As a result, there is a need to find and use complementary alternative data sources such as remote sensing and Earth Observation, modelling and maybe citizen science in the future. In addition, there is a need for improved capacity building, including data analysis, data management, and data sharing policies.

Limitations to data sharing can be explained by the following feedback:

- A “north-south” divide where data is provided to funded projects, with limited benefit to in-country data providers.
- Past experiences where collaborators requested data who then went on to use the data without citing or acknowledging the data sources. There were also concerns that the shared data is being used without permissions, impacting planned publications by the data providers.
- There is a lack of data sharing policies/protocols, with these sometimes being specific to the country or organisation/institution or limited by clauses in donor-funded projects. Thus, a standard protocol for data sharing is needed to ensure data providers retain data ownership and recognition. An example to use is the existing data repository such as IGRAC - International Groundwater Resources Assessment Centre, the which allows data providers to select from different levels of data sharing.

- Development of a common data-management system, with agreed data types and formats that allows for better collaboration between organisations/institutions/countries. This database option should have ownership by the data providers to ensure maintenance and longevity. There is a general lack of internal databases to store data in an easily accessible format, exacerbated when databases are shared between organisations/institutions/countries. Due to a lack of standard formats, there can be data structuring and formatting problems. As a result, there was a consensus that there is need to agree at the start of a project/initiative on a common data-management system, with agreed data types and formats that allows for better collaboration between organisations/institutions/countries. In some countries, it was noted that there is a need for enhanced data sharing via a central validated repository; however, it was noted that this is currently not incentivised, and that this would need long-term funding to collect, maintain and make data available to the database.
- While databases were developed with useful data, these were noted to be specific to a project with maintenance stopping after the project ended; thereby resulting in a loss of access to data by stakeholders.
- There was a call for in-country capacity building in the beneficial aspects of data sharing, responsible use of data and implementing advanced monitoring technology such as EO and optical sensors, as well as data storage, processing and analysis.

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